

EFFECT OF EXHAUST GAS RECIRCULATION ON ENGINE PERFORMANCE AND EMISSION ON VARIABLE COMPRESSION RATIO ENGINE

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ABSTRACT

An internal combustion engine is having a better efficiency, maximum power with less maintenance cost. Because of that Internal Combustion Engines are increased worldwide. It is the very important power source for the automobile vehicles. Now a present emission norm becomes strict and very difficult for any I.C. Engine. The main pollutant are CO, CO₂, HC, NO_x, PM, soot, etc from which NO_x are one of the most harmful component. Nitric Oxide affects the human, other living organisms and environment. It is possible to limit the NO_x in the atmosphere by various methods like exhaust gas recirculation (EGR), catalyst or SCR and water injection. The aim of this work is to find the effect of exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) to reduce the NO_x emission from the I. C. Engine with measuring the all pollutants for different EGR rate with different load condition and find the optimum condition of emission and performance. It is found that adding EGR to the fresh air it is useful to reduce the NO_x emission. Reductions in NO_x emission are achieved by previous research with 5% to 30% EGR rate. However, EGR has other effects on combustion and emission production.

INTRODUCTION

In internal combustion (IC) engines, exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) is a oxide of nitrogen (NO_x) emissions reduction technique used in petrol/gasoline and diesel engines. EGR works by re circulating a partial amount of an engine's exhaust gas back to the engine cylinders.

Avinash Kumar Agarwal, Shravan Kumar Singh [2] They have conducted an experiment on a two-cylinder, direct injection, air-cooled CI engine to observe the effect of exhaust gas recirculation on the exhaust gas temperature and exhaust opacity. It is seen that exhaust gas temperature reduces drastically by employing EGR. Thermal efficiency and brake specific fuel consumption are not affected significantly by EGR. However particulate matter emission in the exhaust increases.

Baert R. S. , Beckman D.E., et al.[3] They have studied Efficient EGR technology for future HD diesel engine emission targets In this study, this research has been extrapolated towards lower emission levels. Exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) was applied to a modern EURO-3-type HD diesel engine. The corresponding fuel matrix covers a range of fuel oxygen mass fractions up to 15%. Results are presented and the impact of fuel oxygen mass fraction and Cetane Number are analysed and compared with results from previous research.

Moser FX, Sams T, et al. [4] They have studied Impact of future exhaust gas emission legislation on heavy duty truck engine. Exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) is an upcoming technology for heavy duty (HD) engines They studied to modern power cylinder technologies to EGR driven needs and concluded that NO_x is reduced by EGR technique and PM increases.

K.Rajan and K.R.Senthilkumar [5] They have studied the effect of EGR on the performance and emission characteristic of diesel engine with Sunflower Oil Methyl Ester. They observed that B20 SFME with 15% EGR rate produce 25% less NO_x emissions compared to diesel fuel for the same level smoke emissions.

Deepak Agarwal, Shrawan Kumar Singh, et al. [6] They investigate the effect of EGR on soot deposits, and wear of vital engine parts, especially piston rings, apart from performance and emissions in a two cylinder, air cooled, constant speed direct injection diesel engine, Reductions in NO_x and exhaust gas temperature were observed but emissions of particulate matter (PM), HC and CO were found to have increased with usage of EGR.

Ladommatos N., R. Balian, et al. [1] In this paper studied about the effects of exhaust gas recirculation on diesel combustion and emissions. The investigation was carried out on a high speed direct injection diesel engine running at an intermediate speed and load. It was found that very large reduction in exhaust NO_x at the expense of higher particulate emission.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP:

The experimental set-up is shown in Figure 1, which is computerized single cylinder four stroke, naturally aspirated, direct injection and water cooled, diesel engine. The specifications of the test engine are given below.

Engine is loaded with an eddy current dynamometer. Engine is equipped with piezoelectric transducer for measuring the pressure variation in the cylinder and AVL 615 Indimeter software which measures the heat release rate from the measured values of cylinder pressure at different crank angle. AVL DiGas 444 five gas analyzer was used for measuring the CO, UHC, NOx, CO2 and AVL Smoke meter was used for measuring the smoke opacity. For circulation of exhaust gases into the intake manifold an EGR set up was provided which consists of a control valve and manometer. For obtaining cold EGR exhaust gas is been stored in a tank and cooled to a predefined temperature before it is send back into the cylinder. The amount of exhaust gas recirculated is calculated before it is send into the engine. The amount of exhaust gas recirculated is calculated using the following formula,

$$\% \text{ EGR} = \frac{\text{Mass of EGR}}{\text{Total intake charge into the cylinder}} \times 100$$

In the present experiment the mass of flow of the exhaust gas is controlled by a valve. The exhaust gas is recirculated into the stream of fresh air which is taken from the atmosphere through a pipe. The exhaust gas and fresh air are mixed with each other before they are send into the cylinder. Both the flow rates of the fresh air and exhaust air air are calculated using a U- tube manometer.

b.Engine specification

Variable Compression Ratio Diesel Engine

No of Cylinder=1

No of Stroke=4

Fuel= Diesel

Vertical, water cooled

Power=3.5 KW, 1500 RPM

Modified VCR Engine Compression Range =12 to 18

Cylinder Diameter=87.5mm

Fig 1 Line diagram of experimental setup

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The engine is operated at a constant speed of 1500 rpm. The first stage of experiment was performed with diesel at different loads from no-load to full load (0%,25%,50%,75%,100%) without EGR at constant speed and different compression ratio (15,16,17,17.5,18). Engine loads are adjusted by using eddy current dynamometer. Exhaust gases are tapped from exhaust pipe and connected to inlet airflow passage with water cooled heat exchanger, so the EGR is cold EGR. The rate of EGR is varied with the help of EGR control valve which is fixed in the pipe control. The second stage of experiment was performed with diesel at different loads from no-load to full load (0%,25%,50%,75%,100%) with EGR rates such as 0%, 5%,10%,15% and 20% at constant speed and different compression ratio (15,16,17,17.5,18). Engine loads are adjusted by using eddy current dynamometer

RESULT AND DISSCUSSION

A.PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

I.BRAKE THERMAL EFFICIENCY (BTE)

Results obtained by performing the experiment are presented in the graphical form as shown in the below graphs. The variation of the brake thermal efficiency along the different loads is presented in graph by taking load on X axis and BTE on Y axis as shown in figure 2. It is clearly seen from the graph that the brake thermal efficiency increases with the load and the maximum possible brake thermal efficiency will be at the maximum load.

Fig 2 Variation of Brake Thermal Efficiency with load for different percentages of EGR

II.VOLUMETRIC EFFICIENCY

The variation of the specific fuel consumption (SFC) along the different loads and different EGR is presented in graph by taking load on X axis and SFC on Y axis as shown in figure 3. It can be observed from the graph that brake specific fuel consumption decreases as the load increases.

FIGURE 3 VARIATION OF LOAD VS VOLUMETRIC EFFICIENCY

B.EMISSION ANALYSIS

I.CO EMISSIONS

The variation of the CO emissions along the different loads is presented in graph by taking load on X axis and CO on Y axis as shown in figure 4. It shows that CO increases with EGR.

Figure 4. variation of Load Vs CO

II.NO EMISSIONS

The variation of the NO_x emissions along the different loads is presented in graph by taking load on X axis and NO_x on Y axis as shown in figure 6. Graph shows that the NO is reduced when EGR is increased.

Figure 5 variation of Load Vs NO

CONCLUSION

EGR is a very useful technique for reducing the NO_x emission. EGR displaces oxygen in the intake air and dilute the intake charge by exhaust gas recirculated to the combustion chamber. Recirculated exhaust gas lower the oxygen concentration in combustion chamber and increase the specific heat of the intake air mixture, which results in lower flame temperatures. It was observed that 20% EGR rate is found to be effective to reduce NO_x emission substantially without deteriorating engine performance in terms of thermal efficiency, bsfc and emissions. Thus, it can be concluded that higher rate of EGR can be applied at lower loads and lower rate of EGR can be applied at higher load. EGR can be applied to diesel engine without sacrificing its efficiency and fuel economy and NO_x reduction can thus be achieved.

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